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The Efficiency of Social Psychology: Sociology of a Technocratic Belief under the French Fourth Republic

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Abstract

This essay surveys the social foundations of a widely shared belief among the French planners of the Fourth Republic (1946-1958): the efficiency of social psychology. It intends to explain the technocratic credit granted to this speciality in the context of the “Productivity campaign”. On the basis of primary and secondary sources (archives of the Commissariat Général au Plan, original texts, specialized literature, etc.), of the bibliometric and content analysis methods, this study emphasizes the role of social tensions in the rise of social psychology and establishes that the examined belief is, among other factors, on a) the progressive familiarization of high ranking French civil-servants with human and social sciences since 1870; b) the state of development of expertise in the United S and the integration of social psychology in the Plan Marshall “Technical assistance program” as well as on c) the professional strategies of French academics and experts. The study concludes that this technological transfer requires to be seized within the frame of a political sociology of human and social sciences.

Key-words: social psychology, technocratic belief, planners, expertise, symbolic power.

Résumé

Cet article prend pour objet les fondements sociaux d'une croyance largement partagée par les planificateurs français de la IV^e République (1946-1958) : l'efficacité de la psychologie sociale. Il vise à rendre compte du crédit technocratique accordé à cette spécialité sociale dans le cadre de la « Campagne de productivité ». À partir de sources primaires et secondaires (archives du Commissariat général au Plan, textes originaux, littérature spécialisée, etc.), de la méthode bibliométrique et de celle l'analyse de contenu, ce travail souligne le rôle des tensions sociales dans l'émergence de la psychologie sociale et met en évidence que la croyance étudiée est notamment fondée, entre autre facteurs, sur a) la familiarisation progressive des hauts-fonctionnaires français avec les sciences humaines et sociales depuis 1870 ; b) l'état de développement de l'expertise aux États-Unis et l'intégration de la psychologie sociale dans le programme d'« assistance technique » du Plan Marshall ainsi que sur c) les stratégies professionnelles des universitaires et experts français. L'étude conclue que ce transfert technologique gagne à être appréhendé dans le cadre d'une sociologie politique des sciences humaines et sociales.

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“The profound cause of our low productivity and the most important one is psychological. No recovery will be possible without a will to recover ; this resoluteness will only arise if it corresponds to a need felt among the population. It is necessary to prepare public opinion, to create a state of mind. It is that state of mind that is lacking in France²”

French productivity taskforce, 1948.

A number of French studies in the history of economy, in the history of psychology as well as several biographical accounts have shown the importance of the national planners’ role in the promotion of social psychology during the Marshall Plan (commissions, publications, funding, etc.) [Drouard, 1983 ; Barjot, 2002 ; Ohayon, 2006]. These narratives that share a common interest in the question of origins also enlighten the history of human and social sciences in France with regards to the political history of the French reconstruction, of the “Trentes glorieuses” and, more generally, the cold war. This shadowy past can obviously be apprehended from different standpoints : expert practice, policy-making, academia, management, trade unionism, etc. In this study, we will emphasize in particular the perspective of civil servant planners and present the reasons that help understand the political faith applied social psychology raised in Fourth Republic France.

At first glance, the problem can appear blatantly obvious: the specialty was politically supported for economical purposes. While this statement is certainly true, it nevertheless fails to answer the following questions: how is it possible to account for the administrative success of this discipline in particular? For what reasons did the planners tend to apprehend the problem they were mandated to solve in psychological terms? To grasp the meaning of this apparently spontaneous trustfulness, one needs to consider historically the relations developed between politicians and economists with this miscellaneous discipline since the late nineteenth century. We will therefore briefly display the evolution of these bonds until the Second World War. Besides, in order to understand mid-century political psychologism as well as the relatively easy reception of the new expert knowledge, it is necessary to seize the

² Groupe de travail de la productivité, *Programme français pour l’accroissement de la productivité (exemplaire provisoire)*, Commissariat général au Plan, [n. d.], p. 11. Archives nationales, AJ 81 176. Emphasized in the original document, most probably issued in late 1948.

nature of the social tie relating French planners to their American counterpart: the famous “Marshall Planners” and their “Special Representatives in Europe” (SRE).

At last, a rarely mentioned factor should be taken in account when attempting to explain applied social psychology’s early triumph in France but also Italy: the political power of (trade-unionist) communists.

The Psychologization of French Political Categories of Thought (1870-1945)

The postwar recognition of human and social sciences as governmentality tools was the outcome of a long legitimization process. The “preparatory notes” of *Les Origines de la France Contemporaine*, the *opus magnum* of Hippolyte Taine, considered as the founder of collective psychology in France (Carroy et al., 2006), helping understand the political importance of human sciences at the beginning of the Third Republic:

“The general cause of the French Revolution as well as our instable social state is hasty, hurried, a priori science, adding to it’s flame and flag to the passions of the mass emancipated by the first revolution, by the machines, and moreover frenzied by the well-being that machines have spread. The general remedy is well forged, experimental science. There is here an incalculable force, capable of indefinite expansions and empires. The evidence of this force is overwhelming. Even in the precipitated and false state, she has done the French revolution, and, under its bastard form of socialism, our last convulsions” (Taine, 1905, p. 306).

Taine adds: *“ By her partial applications she has built the good government of England and United States (which for the rest, by tradition, practices it instinctively). Her (barbarous) name is sociology. Her exact title is: application to the conduct of human affairs of the science of humanity”* (Ibid, p.307). The author also uses the expression *“psychology applied to history”* (Taine, 1905, p. 259) in a letter to the politician-historian François Guizot who provided Taine material support (“auspices”) “for twenty years”.

The French “psychologie des peuples” (distinct from German *völkerpsychologie*), Franco-Italian crowd psychology as well as military and pedagogical psychology were young specialties that came to be known in diverse social circles. According to our own bibliometrical analysis on applied psychology books published in French between 1870 and 1918 (including the *Essai de psychologie militaire* written by the Romanian military doctor M. Campeano in 1902), we can say with is fairly high degree of certainty that industrial social psychology was then merely inexistent in France. It is only during the 1930’s that economists, whose role in the sphere of psychology had been insignificant, will appear on stage after the Great Crash. They will associate with various human and social science experts and contribute in founding institutions in which the young sciences will be assigned to a play a major role. During the interwar period, Taylorism is at its peak but the crisis, by the discontent its consequences generated drove some employers to develop an interest in potentially pacifying measures.

Ideologically complex and difficult to grasp with contemporary categories, this late interwar period in France is characterized by the birth of an unprecedented economical thought. One book will stand out as a governance handbook setting the path for an “economical humanism”: Jean Coutrot’s *Les Leçons de juin 1936*. In this work, the engineer intended “to prepare and carry out (...) the advent of new social relations in France” (Dard, 1995, p. 138). Coutrot thus establishes in 1936 the *Centre national de l’organisation scientifique du travail* (COST), destined to promote and coordinate initiatives favorable to the rationalization of work. The following year, he also sets up the *Centre d’étude pour les problèmes humains* (CEPH) from which a short-lived *Institute of Applied Psychology* (IPSA) will spring off in 1938. The institute was advertised in the following way : “It’s syllabus (...) thus concerns : either the manner by which we can use the sure data of modern psychology, to better organize the work of our collaborators and put them in the most favorable psychological conditions to good output, or lastly the way we can benefit from the same givens to appease, by clarifying the ‘psychological atmosphere’, certain social conflicts that we have vainly tried to resolve by material type concessions, on the sole economic terrain” (Henry, 2004, p. 58). Confronted with such a straightforward statement, one could think that managerial pamphlets have since then undergone a slight euphemization process.

It is now time to briefly address the problem of applied psychology under the Vichy regime (1940-1944), certainly not the most documented topic in the historiography of French psychology. During the German occupation, when the number of companies who fulfilled Nazi commissions went from 7000 to merely 14000 (Ferro, 2003), this pedagogical “clarification” continued and was partially ascribed to psychologists. For instance, in 1943, Raymond Bonnardel became “expert psychotechnicien” at the Université de Paris and published *The adaptation of man to his work: a study of social and industrial psychology* (Bonnardel, 1943). Likewise, in 1943, the renowned psychologist Pierre Janet inaugurated the first “*industrial psychology study cycle*” at the *Commission générale de l’organisation scientifique* (CEGOS), a large consulting firm created during the *Interbellum* where Henri Piéron also gave talks. Pierre Janet therein expressed a wish: the one of “reuniting two individuals that precipitately consider themselves as being opposed to one another: the owner and the boss on the one hand, the employee and the worker on the other” (Ohayon, 2006, p. 268). Of course, psychologists also encountered serious problems during the war : Georges Politzer, whose work influenced, to say the least, Daniel Lagache’s clinical psychology (Dagfal, 2002), was tortured and executed as a communist while Jean-Maurice Lahy, also communist but additionally Jewish, died after having to live a clandestine life. Some opposed resistance within academia. For example, Henri Wallon and his comrade René Zazzo founded the “Front national universitaire » and launched a clandestine brochure called *L’Université libre*.

The Vichy atmosphere was propitious to leadership studies and elite education. The microsociological current of social psychology actually formed itself around the question of the “commandement”, the “chef” or the “meneur” (ringleader). In 1941, Daniel Lagache drafted a programmatic article entitled “Psychology and present times” essentially addressed to Policy-makers. The paper was published in the journal *Éducation*, not exactly a libertarian

review. The author writes : “*The collective need for psychologists becomes even more urgent in a country that, breaking with the immediate past, consciously seeks to pick-up a tradition and rationally organize its future*” (Lagache, 1977, p. 364). The author adds : “*Among the domains that a National revolution³ opens to psychology, the largest, the one from which the most insistant calls stem from, is undoubtedly the domain of pedagogy*” (Ibid., p. 364). Daniel Lagache finally addresses the problem of “chiefs” selection and suggests that the application of “leader psychology” could help the “collective organization” to accomplish some progress.

One can say without any anguish to be mistaking that the Liberation of France generated a political shift within psychology. As a matter of fact, Daniel Lagache will grasp this opportunity since he then proposed to the Ministry of Public Instruction 1945 an overall psychology program in a way that we are already familiar with: “*The collective need for psychologists becomes even more urgent in a country that, breaking with the immediate past, seeks to rationally organize its future.*” (Ohayon, 2006, p. 277). The relevance of such an example does not so much rest upon the fact that it enlightens the practical sense of Daniel Lagache; it more generally (sociologically) lies in that it illustrates the role played by scholars in the building of extra-academic ties in order to promote their current within a competitive field.

We have seen that a certain number of sociohistorical factors (scientificization of political thought and bureaucratic conduct, scientific accommodation and socialization of political personnel, rapid sociopolitical changes, industrialization, etc.) have partly contributed to form certain technocratic expectations towards scholars and social sciences. It is henceforth necessary to explain why these rather receptive dispositions will perennate and, eventually, consolidate.

French Planners and social psychology at the dawn of the “Trente glorieuses”

By what means is it possible to explain the political faith granted to social science in the postwar years? To answer this question, one must, at some point or another, consider the amazement with which French planners took account of the state of development of applied social science overseas. This enchantment, occasionally tempered by envy or disdain towards “mass culture” or “consumerism”, came along with social shame regarding “French retardation” (“le retard français”). Needless to say this ambivalence was probably shared by many local elites engaged in US backed modernization processes.

The abstracted “Frenchman” (“le français”) tended for example to be apprehended as a stubborn and retrograde figure. Two representatives can be exhumed: the peasant and the communist trade-unionist, the first risking to mutate into the second during the rural flight. A fairly good indicator of postwar ideological changes, mythical oppositions and self-denigration bashes, can be found in productivity discourses. In trying to defining “productivity”, Robert Buron, the minister of economic affairs in 1953 writes : “*it is the healthy desire of the modern and the new as well as the refusal of security in mediocrity*”

³ The National revolution (*Révolution nationale*) was the official ideology of the Vichy government.

(Buron, 1953, p. 10). Of course, this sounds terribly common today. But one must recall that this social philosophy was not yet *doxa* in France.

It would yet be wrong to think that only “le français moyen” represented a target for the new slogan sciences. In effect, certain traditional elites, rather poorly prepared for the new relaxed US presentation of self skills, did show signs of skepticism concerning human relations. However, member of this subgroup represented a far less important obstacle than the more numerous Cominform backed trade-unionists criticizing aspects of the Marshall Plan (Carew, 1987).

If the hardnosed trade unionists and classical paternalism holders were not the most predisposed to welcome soothing post-taylorist management, young entrepreneurs, white collars or planners generally represented *per contra* a very receptive audience (Boltanski, 1983). It should still be said that this receptivity was somehow necessary in the case of planners since not everything was contractual in the Marshall Plan contract, to speak like Durkheim. Certain practices were indeed imposed or discouraged, such as “Restrictive Business Practices” (RBP’s). One of the promoted behaviors was a set of “non directive” communication patterns intended to replace old school “commandement”, a style US experts abominated, by “democratic leadership”.

The political flipside of an economical mandate

The mandate ascribed to the new experts was not solely economical, it was simultaneously political. As it was applied in the 1950’s in Western Europe and in Japan US social psychology, social psychology represented a) a structuring structure : as an instrument of knowledge and of construction of the world (leader/follower, authoritarianism/democratism, change/resistance, etc.), b) a structured structure (it could take the form of a communication mean as in “human relations”), as well as c) an instrument of domination, not only to the extent that it was very generally applied in a top-down direction (on what occasions, for example, could workers call upon psychological experts to overcome executive “resistance to change”?) but also in its tendency to reduce power relations to simple communication ones, social relations between groups to interactions between individuals.

In order to concretely understand the shifts being introduced in the workplace, it is most interesting to analyze the original instructions (translated from English into French) given to the trainees of two major training sessions financed by the *Commissariat général à la productivité* in 1956. Within small groups, employers, managers and technicians were education in the art of “informal” and “free discussion” (Arbousse-Bastide, 1959). The rules enclosed : being on first name basis with one another, becoming more straightforward and “spontaneous”, switching from V to T form and, last but not least, forgetting about “hierarchical presuppositions” (Pagès, 1959).

There are reasons to believe that France, and probably other Marshall Plan countries, were swept by an “institutionalization of condescension strategies” (Arnault, 2011), strategies by which “*agents occupying a superior position within one the hierarchies of the objective space symbolically deny the social distance that doesn’t however cease to exist, thus insuring*

oneself the profits of the recognition granted to a purely symbolic denegation of distance” (Bourdieu, 1987, p. 152). These new communications rules, inviting to simplify (hierarchical) interactions, can also be seen as manifestations of the sociohistorical informalization process analyzed by Cas Wouters. The Dutch eliasian sociologist attributes, among other factors, the informalization of manners in different Anglo-Saxon countries to “*shifts in the balances of power*”. (Wouters, 2007) He also mentions, as an indicator of this type of social change, the spreading of “industrial relations” firms across the US.

In France, planners unquestionably knew that working class categories of thought had been quite deeply shaped by the in-group/out-group oppositions inherent to socialist and communist discourses. As a matter of fact, many wage workers did then possess a relatively unified self-representation as a distinct social class: the “proletariat”. Planners also knew that this “state of mind” represented a serious hindrance to the “Productivity campaign”. The CGP archives actually contain trade-union press clippings with such irreverent titles as “At the Marshall Plan’s Beck and Call : Puppet Rulers and Top Management preach the productivity crusade” (Serdais, 1949).

“Preparing public opinion” was undoubtedly a delicate undertaking, especially when intellectuals sided by the workers more than by the managers. Within the intellectual field and academic ranks, applied (social) psychology raised criticism. In the early 1950’s, Jacques Lacan, George Canguilhem, and even the young Michel Crozier, denounced the instrumental and ideological dimension of industrial expertise (Ohayon, 2006). For example, Paul Fraisse, director of the *Laboratoire de psychologie expérimentale et de physiologie des sensations of the École pratique des hautes études* (EPHE), criticized the “human relations” trend (supported by his competitor Daniel Lagache) in an article published in *Esprit*; a highly regarded non communist review. In this paper, entitled “Human Relations : Progress or Mystification ?”, he exposed his longing to see trade unions “*outsmart management’s maneuver consisting in breaking workers solidarity*” (Fraisse and Guibourg, 1953, p. 803). It should be noted that the author, that himself conducted a “psychotechnical mission” in the US within the Marshall Plan agreements omits to mention the French planner’s role in the “mystification” he denounces. However, this essay, among others, proves that no consensus existed concerning the social uses of social sciences.

To conclude and avoid misunderstandings, it is worthwhile to make clear that, firstly, social psychology is in no way reducible to its industrial applications and that, secondly, interrogations consisting in finding out if it was or not wise to import industrial social psychology in Western Europe do not represent research questions. In other words, proposing a critical account of the globalization of “human relations” does not mechanically imply that it would have been preferable to convey Stakhanovism in its place. The sociohistorical problem rather consists in rereading the diffusion of social psychology beyond the Marshall Plan’s frame to intellectually reintegrate the transnational process within the context of the cultural cold war. It is a matter of proposing a *political* sociology of social sciences aiming at shedding more light on the nexus of social relations constituent of their historical unconscious (Bourdieu, 2000) : a task that is far from being achieved in a country that, in this respect, certainly lags behind the United States.

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